
163. Dual active galactic nuclei

THIS ESSAY IS another on the theme of Gaia's contributions to cosmology. It is centred on the perhaps surprising fact that Gaia can identify *binary* supermassive black holes in active galaxies, and with sufficiently small angular separations that can pinpoint in-spiralling black holes well on their way to their eventual merger.

THE REALISATION that active galaxies and quasars host **supermassive black holes** at their centres is a long story. It dates back some 60 years to Maarten Schmidt's early attempts to explain the emission-line spectrum of the radio source 3C 273, and Hoyle & Fowler's proposal that H-burning supermassive stars could explain the compact dimensions and high energy output of quasars.

In 1970, Wolfe & Burbidge argued that the large velocity dispersion of stars in the central regions of elliptical galaxies could only be explained by a large mass concentration, of order $10^{10} M_{\odot}$. Dynamical evidence for a massive dark object at the core of M87 was presented in 1978, and further supported by high-angular resolution observations by the Hubble Space Telescope in 1994.

Fast forwarding over many other theoretical and observational contributions, and other candidate supermassive black holes (including at the centre of our own Galaxy), the consensus today is that all quasars, Seyfert galaxies, and active galactic nuclei (AGN) in general, host a matter-accreting massive black hole at their cores.

LEAVING ASIDE details of their initial formation, especially of primordial black holes early on in the history of the Universe, cosmological models of structure formation within the Λ CDM framework all predict the widespread existence of a population of *dual* supermassive black holes inside their common host galaxy.

Such dual supermassive black hole systems are held to be the result of galaxy mergers. The in-spiralling black holes, within the merged galaxy, will themselves eventually merge, giving rise to a burst of intense gravitational waves. The first observation of such gravitational waves was made in 2015, when a black hole merger signal was picked up by the LIGO gravitational wave detectors.

AT A TIME when there was little observational evidence for the existence of massive *binary* black holes, Yu (2002) studied their occurrence, merger history, and lifetimes in the hierarchical model of galaxy formation, and examined the consequences '*... if no evidence of binary black holes is found in active galactic nuclei*'.

To my knowledge, the first clear evidence for a supermassive binary black hole system came with the Chandra X-ray observations of 3C 75, the double radio source at the centre of Abell 400. Hudson et al. (2006) resolved the two active galactic nuclei, concluding that they are a bound system resulting from a previous merger.

These and subsequent observations were guided by significant improvements in large-scale hydrodynamic cosmological simulations, which began to make detailed predictions for the evolution of the baryonic structures in the Universe, including galaxy mergers.

Drawing on these simulations of galaxy mergers, close pairs of supermassive black holes can form when both (pre-merger) progenitor galaxies host such an object. When separated by a few kiloparsec, they can be observed either as dual AGN (when both black holes are observed as active), or as 'offset AGN' (and displaced from the galaxy centre) either when only one is active, or when signalling a recoiling black hole after a binary merger (Steinborn et al., 2016; Capelo et al., 2017).

OBSERVATIONAL EFFORTS to find dual AGN have intensified over the past decade, in part to verify the findings of these structure formation and merger simulations. And although simulations suggest that the fraction of dual active galactic nuclei increases with redshift (Rosas-Guevara et al., 2019), progress is challenged by the fact that discovering them, at kpc-scale separations, even in the local Universe, requires high-resolution observations of large numbers of candidate objects.

I should also stress that the appearance of multiple active galactic nuclei at small angular separations can also be due to gravitational lensing of single sources (essay 161), with follow-up spectroscopy often being crucial in distinguishing between the two effects.

High-resolution Ks band Large Binocular Telescope images ($2.2 \times 2.2 \text{ arcsec}^2$) of five Gaia ‘multi-peak’ AGN discoveries, showing redshifts and separations (Mannucci et al., 2023).

A NUMBER OF candidates have been discovered with SDSS spectroscopy, from which Liu et al. (2011b) estimated the fraction of dual AGN at just 1.3% within 30 kpc. The first triple system was also discovered from SDSS spectroscopy by Liu et al. (2011a): the three black holes, with masses $\sim 10^8 M_\odot$, are predicted to merge in ~ 40 Myr. Others were found from the SDSS–MaNGA spectroscopic survey (Fu et al., 2023). Bhattacharya et al. (2023) searched one million SDSS images, finding 159 dual AGN candidates, with just two triple systems.

Some 100 candidates (but with just 3 confirmed) have been found with the Hyper Suprime–Cam on Subaru (Silverman et al., 2020). High-resolution follow-up observations have been made with JWST–NIRSpec (Perna et al., 2023a; Perna et al., 2023b), and at multi-wavelengths including X-ray by De Rosa et al. (2023).

While a key question is whether their numbers match the predictions of cosmological simulations, especially at high- z (Perna et al., 2023a), it remains the case that only a few confirmed examples have been found at $z > 0.5$: Mannucci et al. (2022) noted that just four had separations below 8 kpc at $z > 1$.

I WILL NOW focus on some recent contributions with Gaia, where the instrument’s sub-arcsec along-scan angular resolution is generating its own survey of active galactic nuclei. Various approaches are being followed.

The first, which the authors have dubbed ‘varstrometry’ for ‘intrinsic variability induced astrometric jitter’, exploits one of the approaches used for the astrometric detection of unresolved binary stars with Hipparcos, viz. one component varying in luminosity leads to the astrometric motion of the system’s *photocentre*. The phenomenon was already termed ‘VIMs’, for ‘variability induced movers’ (Wielen, 1996), and 288 multiple star solutions were classified as VIMs in the Hipparcos catalogue (Lindegren et al., 1997). A similar scheme is being exploited for Gaia (Pourbaix et al., 2022, §7.2.6).

As developed in the Gaia–AGN context by Hwang et al. (2020), the idea is to detect any temporal displacements of the photocentre in unresolved (sub-kpc separation) optically selected dual active galactic nuclei.

Shen et al. (2019) then used DR2 astrometry, including the ‘astrometric excess noise’ (Lindegren et al., 2018, Eq. 12), to constrain the off-nucleus population of a low-redshift ($z = 0.3–0.8$) sample of active galactic nuclei. These were selected from the Sloan Digital Sky Survey as showing significant photometric variability.

They found that Gaia DR2 already provided strong constraints on the projected off-nucleus distance at these redshifts: 99%, 90%, and 40% must be centred to better than 1 kpc, 500 pc, and 100 pc, respectively. They concluded that ‘offset AGN’, those displaced by more than a few hundred pc, must be rare at low redshift.

Chen et al. (2022) used the same approach to detect unresolved quasar pairs, also based on Gaia DR2. Their follow-up snapshot imaging observations with HST–WFC3 showed a high fraction of resolved systems amongst the 45 observed, but without be able to distinguish dual nuclei from lensed systems.

Shen et al. (2023) searched for multiple Gaia sources corresponding to a single SDSS target, and found 60 resolved candidates, although again unable to distinguish dual nuclei from lensed systems.

Similar studies by Ji et al. (2023) identified 143 SDSS spectroscopically confirmed quasars that have multiple Gaia EDR3 detections within 1 arcsec of the quasar position. Based on spectral-fitting, they found two *bona fide* double quasars, and 56 other candidates.

Chen et al. (2023) searched in DR2, but made their analysis with DR3 astrometry. Follow-up VLBA radio observations of 27 candidates revealed 8 systems with either multiple radio components, or system offsets.

A DIFFERENT approach was used by Mannucci et al. (2022), who searched for AGNs showing multiple peaks in their Gaia light profiles. All of their 221 candidates (at $z = 0.3–4$) followed up with high-resolution images (26 archival HST, and 5 from LBT) showed multiple components with sub-arcsec separation, confirming the high reliability of this selection method.

Various follow-up studies have been made for these multiple-peak candidates. Ciurlo et al. (2023) found 2 dual AGNs out of 4 candidates observed with integral-field spectroscopy. Gross et al. (2023) established one as a lensed quasar. Scialpi et al. (2023) observed 12 with VLT–MUSE, and classified 5 as dual AGNs, 2 as lensed systems, and 5 as chance alignments of foreground stars. Wang et al. (2023) observed 5 candidates with e–MERLIN, and detected significant radio offsets in four.

DUAL ACTIVE GALACTIC NUCLEI, we now know, provide an important probe of the physical processes that drive the in-spiralling of supermassive black hole pairs inside a single merged galaxy. Difficult to detect and characterise, Gaia is making a significant contribution to their discovery.